

Scientific Computation Survey

1. Email *

2. 1.1 Name, department, advisor, position

3. 1.2 Summary of Research Goals

Programming Experience

4. 2.1 How long have you been programming?

Mark only one oval.

< 1 year

1-3 year

3-5 year

More than 5 years

5. 2.2 What was your first programming language?

Mark only one oval.

- C/C++
- Python
- Java
- Matlab
- Other: _____

6. 2.3 Have you attended any special training (seminars, workshops, tutorials, etc.) to assist your programming needs **in the past year**?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Other: _____

7. 2.4a When was the last time that you learned a new programming language/paradigm for your programming needs?

8. 2.4b What was the programming lang

9. 2.4c and how long did that take for you to feel comfortable with it?

Mark only one oval.

Hours

A few days

A few weeks

A few months

Other: _____

10. 2.5 What programming language(s) do you use?

Check all that apply.

C/C++

Java

Python

Matlab

Julia

Other: _____

11. 2.6 What is the primary reason that you use the language(s) that you do?

12. 2.7 Do you usually write software to automate mundane tasks (like transferring data, making plots)?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

13. 2.8 What operating systems do you primarily use (for everyday use and for programming)?

Check all that apply.

MacOS

Linux

Windows

Other: _____

14. 2.9 How long does the code you write stick around?

Mark only one oval.

- One-time/Ad-hoc
- A few weeks to a few months (<1 year)
- 1~2 year
- > 2 year

15. 2.10 When programming, do you aim for performance (e.g., use of parallelism)?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

16. 2.11 When programming, do you aim for portability and reusability?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

Research Software Stack

The following questions are focused on the main research project(s) that you are working on currently.

17. 3.1 Please describe the purpose of this research project.

18. 3.2 What is the software stack for your current research project? (Applications, programming language and environment (like Jupyter notebook etc), and libraries commonly used, ...)

19. 3.3 Is the source code of said software available to the public (if so, the link to it)? (including the main libraries or application that your software depends on)

Mark only one oval.

No

Other: _____

20. 3.4 In what programming languages are the softwares written in?

Check all that apply.

- C/C++
 Java
 Python
 Matlab
 Fortran
 Other: _____

21. 3.5 What programs/libraries does this software stack use for numerical computation?

Check all that apply.

- Numpy/Scipy
 Matlab libraries
 Other: _____

22. 3.6 How large is the codebase of this project (in lines of code if possible)?

Mark only one oval.

- Not aware
 Tens lines
 Hundreds lines
 Thousands lines
 Other: _____

23. 3.7 How many people contribute to this project? (At least looks at the code)

Mark only one oval.

1

2

3

4

5

6

Other: _____

24. 3.8 Are there research staff dedicated to programming for this project? (To research assistant write in other if the interviewee mention some degrees of contribution from research staff)

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Other: _____

25. 3.9 When was the majority of this project written?

Mark only one oval.

< 1 year ago

1-3 years ago

3-5 year ago

Other: _____

26. 3.10 On what machines do you typically run your software on (server, cluster, supercomputer etc.)? (To research assistant: if any name gets mentioned, put in other)

Check all that apply.

- Personal Computer (or one that you are the only user of it)
- Personal Server (or one that you are the only user of it)
- Group Server
- Cluster
- Supercomputer (Oak Ridge or something, way bigger than della)
- Other: _____

27. 3.11 Are these machines dedicated to your projects or shared with others?

Mark only one oval.

- Dedicated
- Shared
- Other: _____

28. 3.12 Does this project require specific hardware (GPU, TPU, FPGA, etc?)

Check all that apply.

- GPU
- FPGA
- TPU
- Other: _____

29. 3.13 Do you use any programming tools specialized for the specific hardware (e.g. CUDA for GPU, Tensorflow on TPUs)?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

30. 3.14 Do you use any job submission system (e.g. slurm, condor) for this project?

Check all that apply.

Slurm

Condor

No

Other: _____

Performance Optimization and Parallelism

31. 4.1 What percentage of research time is spent actively waiting for runs (i.e., the main research has to be stalled, if you are working on other important tasks on the same project while waiting it does not count toward actively waiting.)?

Mark only one oval.

< 5%

5-10%

10-20%

20-50%

> 50%

Other: _____

32. 4.2 Do you think the computation performance behavior of the project is unsatisfactory?

Mark only one oval.

Yes, it is unsatisfactory

No, it is satisfactory

33. 4.3 Are your **bigger** research plans unattainable due to lack of computation power?

Mark only one oval.

Yes, bigger plans are unattainable due to lack of computation power

No, all plans can be carried out with current computation

34. 4.4 Is additional computation blocked by computation speed or lack of memory or something else?

Check all that apply.

Computation Speed

Memory

Other: _____

35. 4.5 Do you spend time optimizing your programs for performance?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

36. 4.5a (if Yes to 5) What optimizations did you do to improve the performance?

37. 4.6 Do you use any programming profiling tools/techniques (i.e., to get hot functions/loops) and if so, which ones or how?

Mark only one oval.

No

Other: _____

38. 4.7 Are you aware of different forms of parallelism (task/data/pipelined)? (A simple form of parallelism is running multiple jobs currently)

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

39. 4.8 Do you currently use any form of parallelism in your research? (If answer is "no", skip 4.9 4.13 and 5.7)

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

40. 4.9 Do you currently use any job based parallelism (multiple runs in parallel with no interaction)?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No (or no to 4.8)

41. 4.10 Do you currently use any process-based parallelism (eg.MPI)?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No (or no to 4.8)

42. 4.11 Do you currently use any shared-memory parallelism (e.g. pthreads/OpenMP)?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No (or no to 4.8)

43. 4.12 Do you optimize parallel code?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No (or no to 4.8)

44. 4.13 Do you use parallel libraries as a black box?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No (or no to 4.8)

Developing & Debugging

45. 5.1 For the current project, are bigger research plans unattainable due to lack of programming expertise as a group?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, bigger plans are unattainable due to lack of programming expertise
- No, research plans can be carried out.

46. 5.2 Do you use an IDE and if so, what features are most helpful?

Check all that apply.

- Syntax highlighting
- Debugging (breakpoint etc)
- Autocomplete
- Program analysis and related compiler feedback
- Interaction (like Jupyter Notebook)
- Other: _____

47. 5.3 For the current project, what percentage of research time is spent in programming (including debugging)?

Mark only one oval.

- <1%
- 1-5%
- 5-10%
- 10-20%
- 20-50%
- 50-90%
- >90%
- Other: _____

48. 5.4 Out of the programming time, what percentage is spent in debugging?

Mark only one oval.

- <1%
- 1-10%
- 10-20%
- 20-50%
- 50-90%
- >90%
- Other: _____

49. 5.5 For the current project, after the codebase is relatively developed, how often do you find bugs?

Mark only one oval.

- Almost every time
- Every a few days
- Every a few weeks
- Rarely
- Other: _____

50. 5.6 What debugging techniques/tools do you use?

Check all that apply.

- Looking at code
- Printing
- Breakpoint and step in
- Use debugger (gdb etc)
- Other: _____

51. 5.7 Do you debug parallel code, and if so, how primarily?

Mark only one oval.

- No
- Other: _____

Machine Learning

52. 6.1 Do you use machine learning in your project?
(If answer is “no”, skip 6.2 and 6.3)

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

53. 6.2 For what purpose does this project use machine learning?

Mark only one oval.

N/A

Other: _____

54. 6.3 What software/platform do you use for machine learning tasks?

Check all that apply.

PyTorch

TensorFlow

Other: _____

Future

55. 7.1 How would your research change with 2x, 10x, 100x speedup of the main computation tasks? (Break it down for 2x/10x/100x, is there a difference?)

56. 7.2 How many hours would you be willing to spend to learn a new language or programming technique for 2x, 10x, 100x speedup? (Break it down for 2x/10x/100x, is there a difference?)

57. 7.3 What language(s) would you prefer your codebase was written in?

Check all that apply.

- C/C++
- Python
- Java
- Rust
- Go
- Matlab
- Other: _____

58. 7.4 What features would you like your programming environment (IDE, CLI tools, etc.) to support?

59. 7.5 Is there anything you would like from the CS community (better tools, build systems, IDEs etc.)?

60. 7.6 Is there anything you wished we asked that we did not?

Princeton Research Computing Center Questions (if the interviewee is using Princeton clusters)

61. 8.1 (optional) Have you reached out to Princeton Research Computing Center for questions (when you need help to set up or resources etc)?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Other: _____

62. 8.2 (optional) Are they aware the ticketing system at Princeton Research Computing?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Other: _____

63. 8.3 (optional) If you need to watch a 30-min video and do a quiz before registering for a cluster (about how to get help, ticketing system, common practices), would it block you from registering an account?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Other: _____

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